

DI-XANTHONES. PART I. CHROMONO-2':3'-2:3-XANTHONE

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2:5-Diphenoxyterephthalic acid, prepared by condensing 2:5-dibromoterephthalic acid with sodium phenoxide, using excess of phenol as a solvent or a diluent, in presence of copper powder, has been cyclised by two different methods to yield chromono-2':3'-2:3-xanthone.

Xanthone (I) and its numerous substituted derivatives are known to possess antiseptic and insecticidal properties (Davis and White, *J. Urol.*, 1918, 2, 107; Fischer, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1913, 65, 991). The γ -pyrone structure is a characteristic feature of the xanthone molecule which might contribute, in part, to its properties.

Therefore it was considered worthwhile to prepare organic compounds with two such structural features in the same molecule. Several such compounds are possible. In this communication the preparation of chromono-2':3'-2:3-xanthone or the di-xanthone (II) is reported.

2:5-Dibromoterephthalic acid (III), required for the preparation of this di-xanthone, was obtained from 2:5-dibromo-*p*-xylene according to Marzin (*J. prakt. Chem.*, 1933, 138, 103). The yield of 2:5-dibromo-*p*-toluic acid, reported by Marzin, is not, however, obtainable under the reaction conditions described, but where double the quantity of dilute nitric acid is used and refluxing continued 15 hours, the yield is considerably improved. Some nitration products, insoluble in sodium bicarbonate, have also been found along with 2:5-dibromo-*p*-toluic acid.

Eckert and Seidal (*ibid.*, 1921, 102, 338) have reported the preparation of an acid, supposed to be 2:5-diphenoxyterephthalic acid (IV), by the condensation of 2:5-dibromoterephthalic acid with phenol in the presence of potassium hydroxide and copper powder. This acid (m. p. 314°) is reported to have furnished the di-xanthone (II) when treated with thionyl chloride and anhydrous aluminium chloride. The melting point and the C and H analyses of the di-xanthone have not been reported.

On repeating the experiments of these workers the present authors could not obtain the 2:5-diphenoxyterephthalic acid by this method. The product appeared always to be largely 2:5-dihydroxyterephthalic acid (V), as shown by its m.p., equivalent weight and blue fluorescence in alcohol and water (Hemmelmeyer, *Monatsh.*, 1917, 88, 82; Marzin, *loc. cit.*). This is further supported by our observation that 2:5-dibromoterephthalic acid can be easily hydrolysed to 2:5-dihydroxyterephthalic acid by boiling with a dilute solution of potassium hydroxide. This product, which is largely 2:5-dihydroxyterephthalic acid, is likely to afford an indefinite mixture of substances on treatment with thionyl chloride, followed by anhydrous aluminium chloride.

2:5-Diphenoxyterephthalic acid can, however, be easily obtained by the condensation of one molecular proportion of 2:5-dibromoterephthalic acid with four of sodium phenoxide in the presence of copper powder and a large excess of phenol acting as a solvent or a diluent. For the conversion of the acid and the phenol into sodium salts, the use of absolute ethyl alcohol is necessary. When limz-distilled alcohol was used, the product was found to be a mixture of 2:5-diphenoxyterephthalic acid and 2:5-dihydroxyterephthalic acid.

The di-xanthone (II) was easily obtained by treating pure 2:5-diphenoxyterephthalic acid with phosphorus oxychloride or with phosphorus pentachloride in nitrobenzene, followed by anhydrous aluminium chloride. The impure acid yielded a mixture from which it was difficult to extract the pure di-xanthone.

EXPERIMENTAL

Attempted Condensation of 2:5-Dibromoterephthalic Acid with Phenol in the presence of Potassium Hydroxide and Copper Powder.—2:5-Dibromoterephthalic acid (0.5 g.), phenol (0.29 g.) and KOH (0.71 g.) were dissolved in 10 c.c. of water. A pinch of copper powder was added and the mixture was refluxed for 3 hours in an oil-bath. Copper powder was filtered off and the filtrate was acidified. The yellow product was crystallised from alcohol in small, yellow needles, m.p. 312° (decomp.). (Found: Equiv., 103.7; calc. for 2:5-dihydroxyterephthalic acid, 99; calc. for 2:5-diphenoxyterephthalic acid, 175).

In another experiment the same amounts of 2:5-dibromoterephthalic acid, phenol and about 0.1 g. copper powder were taken in 10 c.c. of KOH solution (conc.) and refluxed for 3 hours in an oil-bath. The product was worked out as above and it had the same physical constants.

Condensation of 2:5-Dibromoterephthalic Acid with Sodium Phenoxide in the presence of Copper Powder and excess of Phenol.—Sodium metal (0.9 g.) was dissolved in absolute alcohol (15 c.c.). 2:5-Dibromoterephthalic acid (2 g.) was dissolved in 20 c.c. of freshly distilled phenol in a 100 c.c. flask by warming and the alcoholic solution of sodium ethoxide was then gradually added to it, followed by 0.1 g. of copper powder and the flask was fitted with a water condenser. Whole of the alcohol was then distilled off. The water condenser was replaced by an air condenser fitted with soda-lime guard-tube and the mixture was heated in an oil-bath at 180° for 3 hours. After cooling, enough ether was added to dissolve out the excess of phenol

and the solution was filtered. The residue was washed with fresh ether till the phenol was completely removed. It was dissolved in water, filtered to remove the copper and the filtrate was acidified. The precipitated substance was filtered, treated with sodium bicarbonate (charcoal), filtered again and decomposed with HCl (dil.), yield 1.4 g. It was twice crystallised from glacial acetic acid to afford a crystalline powder, m.p. 267°. (Found: Equiv., 173, 178. C, 67.65; H, 4.2. $C_{20}H_{14}O_8$ requires equiv., 175; C, 68.28; H, 4.0%).

The Di-xanthone.—(a). 2:5-Diphenoxyterephthalic acid (pure, m.p. 267°) (0.23 g.) was mixed with $POCl_3$ (5 c.c.) and the mixture heated in an oil-bath. A brisk reaction started with the evolution of HCl gas at 95°. The reaction mixture was refluxed for one hour, keeping the bath temperature at 120-25°. $POCl_3$ was then distilled off under reduced pressure and the residue treated with powdered ice and made alkaline with dilute NaOH solution. The insoluble precipitate was filtered, washed free of alkali and dried; yield 0.14 g. It was crystallised from toluene in small, yellow needles, m.p. 404° (aluminium block) with sublimation and slight decomposition. (Found: C, 76.25; H, 3.02. $C_{20}H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 76.4; H, 3.18%).

(b). The pure 2:5-diphenoxyterephthalic acid (0.1 g.) was dissolved in 3 c.c. of freshly distilled nitrobenzene on warming in a 10 c.c. Erlenmeyer flask. To this was added PCl_5 (0.45 g.), followed by $AlCl_3$ (anhyd., 0.2 g.). The mixture was heated on a water-bath for half an hour till the evolution of HCl gas had stopped. Nitrobenzene was removed under reduced pressure and the remaining red residue was treated with ice. The mixture was made alkaline with NaOH solution, filtered and washed free of alkali. The dried product weighed 80 mg. It was crystallised from toluene in yellow crystalline powder, m.p. 404°.